

NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF THE ELASTOPLASTIC BEHAVIOUR OF GFRP LAMINATES

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SUMMARY: A constitutive model for composite materials based on the mixing theory is presented in this work. The model permits to account for different mechanical behaviour of each constituent (elasticity, elasto-plasticity, damage, etc). It analyses the behaviour of the each component separately and it obtains the global performance of the composite through the rule of mixtures. The stiffness of the constituents are modified by means of micro-mechanical models in order that the model accounts for the experimental stiffness in the transverse direction. Experiments were performed to analyse the elasto-plastic behaviour of unidirectional and cross-ply coupons made of glass fibre reinforced epoxy matrix. The numerical results of the constitutive model are compared to the experimental ones.

KEYWORDS : micromechanics, rule of mixtures, finite element method, anisotropy, glass-epoxy laminates.

INTRODUCTION

The design of structural elements using fibre-reinforced polymer-matrix composites requires specific tools capable of taking into account different mechanical properties of the constituents, their high anisotropy and the lack of homogeneity at the microscopic level. In the last few years, several attempts to develop an efficient numerical tool have appeared. However, the correlation between analytical and measured results is, in general, deficient and there is an inability to simulate the behaviour of highly non-linear anisotropic materials by means of conventional codes of finite element method (FEM). This is extremely important in fibre-reinforced materials, which are strongly anisotropic.

Micro and macro-models constitute the alternative to study the mechanical behaviour of composite materials. Micro-models focus the study at micro-mechanical level and they try to simulate the interaction between the reinforcement and the matrix at this level. These models are quite expensive in terms of computation time. Macro-models express the whole composite behaviour as that of a single material. A rule that defines this equivalent single homogenous material is then needed. Most macro-mechanical models are based on the mixing theory. This theory allows to study the behaviour of composite materials as a combination of individual

components, each one with its own constitutive law, satisfying an appropriate closing equation. This equation establishes the inter-material kinematical conditions.

ANISOTROPIC ELASTOPLASTIC CONSTITUTIVE MODEL FOR COMPOSITES

To simulate the non-linear constitutive behaviour of composite materials it is necessary to consider many of their relevant features such as: high anisotropy; existence of several compounding substances; one directional plastic flow of fibres; debonding, leading to the lost of kinematical compatibility; local buckling; tendency of the fibres to arrange in the direction of the higher stress, and large strains. All of these phenomena produce losses in the global strength and stiffness and are the main responsible of the non-linear behaviour of composite materials.

In this work we present a constitutive model that accounts for the non-linear behaviour of composite materials by means of the mixing theory acting on a general anisotropic elastoplastic model for each constituent. Indeed, the anisotropic elastoplastic constitutive model is considered one of the “base” models that can be included in the mixing theory. Although this model has been described in detail in references (Car *et al.*)[1, 2], the main points of the mixing theory are summarised in the next section.

Fig. 1 Schematic flow diagram for the elastoplastic solution of a multiphase material

Mixing Theory

There are several theories that allow to simulate the constitutive behaviour of composite materials by means of an equivalent single material. Among them, *Mixing Theory* is considered one of the most appropriate (Trusdell)[3]. The classic mixing theory is based on the combination and interaction of the basic substances that make up a composite material. This theory is suitable for explaining the behaviour of a point of a composite from the physical-mathematical structure of the mechanics of a continuum. Mixing theory is based on the principle of interaction of the constituents (or phases) with the following hypotheses: i) in each infinitesimal volume of a composite material only a finite number of compounding substances participate; ii) each substance participates in the behaviour of the composite in the same proportion as its volume fraction; iii) all compounds observe kinematical compatibility (closing equation); iv) the volume occupied by each compound is much smaller than the total volume of the composite.

It also assumes that in each material point all the component substances contribute at the same time and with their own constitutive law in the assigned volume fraction. This allows to combine materials with different constitutive behaviour (i.e. elastic, elasto-plastic, elasto-brittle, elasto-damage, etc.). Figure 1 is a diagram showing the formulation of the mixing theory formulation.

The mixing theory is based on the principle that each substance contributes to the behaviour of the composite proportionally to the relative volume that it occupies. The *volumetric participation coefficient* is defined as:

$$k_c = \frac{dV_c}{dV_0} \quad \sum_{c=1}^n k_c = 1$$

where V_c is the volume of each phase and V_0 is the total volume of the composite.

The classic mixing theory assumes that all phases in the mixture have the same strain field at each point. This assumption is equivalent to the hypothesis that the contribution of each component is in parallel. Then the *closing equation* can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij} \equiv (\mathbf{e}_{ij})_1 = (\mathbf{e}_{ij})_2 = \dots = (\mathbf{e}_{ij})_n$$

Neamtu *et al.* [4] proposed a generalisation of the classic mixing theory including the serial and parallel configurations. Therefore, it is possible to define the *closing equation* as:

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij} \equiv (1 - c) \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{par} + c \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{ser}$$

where \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{par} and \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{ser} are the parallel and serial components of the strains defined as

$$\mathbf{e}_{ij}^{par} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{c=1}^n (\mathbf{e}_{ij})_c \quad \mathbf{e}_{ij}^{ser} = \sum_{c=1}^n (\mathbf{e}_{ij})_c$$

and χ is a parameter of ensemble serial-parallel, which can be interpreted like a relaxation between the strict serial or parallel behaviour (figure 2). It is not easy to obtain this parameter, as it should be found by experimental tests or micro-mechanic models, and depends on the interaction between each phase at a micro-mechanical level. This generalized closing equation, at the present moment, is not ready in our FEM code. Therefore the parallel closing equation is used in this work.

Fig 2. Strict parallel and strict serial behaviours for a bi-component lineal composite

In general, composite materials that fulfil the closing equation for strict parallel behaviour also satisfy the basic condition of the additivity of the *free energy function* of their components. This can be expressed as:

$$m\mathbf{y}(\mathbf{e}^e, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{a}^m) = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c m_c \mathbf{y}_c [\mathbf{e}, (\mathbf{e}^p)_c, \mathbf{q}, \mathbf{a}_c^m]$$

where m is the mass; \mathbf{y} is the internal specific energy; \mathbf{e} , \mathbf{e}^e , \mathbf{e}^p , are the total, the elastic and the plastic strain tensor respectively; \mathbf{q} is the absolute temperature and \mathbf{a}^m is a set of internal plastic variables.

As mentioned earlier, the model here presented permits the introduction of different constitutive models for each constituent. In order to analyse a fibre reinforced composite material, a standard isotropic plasticity model has been chosen for the matrix material, whereas the behaviour of the fibre reinforcement is modelled by means of an anisotropic elastoplastic model, which is presented in the next section. Deeper details of this model can be found in references (Car *et al.*)[1, 2].

The global *constitutive equation* of the model allows to calculate the effective stress of the composite material. It is obtained by considering the Clausius-Duhem inequality, the Coleman method (Malvern)[5] and the previous mentioned addition of each component's free energy.

$$\mathbf{s}_{ij} = m^0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{e}_{ij}} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \frac{m^0}{m_c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial (\mathbf{e}_{ij})_c} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \frac{m^0}{m_c} (\mathbf{s}_{ij})_c$$

The total *tangent constitutive tensor* of the composite material is the effective stress variation

respect to the strain space

$$C_{ijkl}^T = \frac{\partial \mathbf{s}_{ij}}{\partial \mathbf{e}_{kl}} = \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{e}_{ij} \otimes \partial \mathbf{e}_{kl}} = \sum_{c=1}^n k_c \frac{m_c^0}{m_c} (C_{ijkl}^T)_c$$

Anisotropic Elasto-plastic Model for a Single Phase.

The constitutive model presented in this section is one of the “base” models which can be introduced in the mixing theory previously introduced. The formulation of a constitutive law adequate to simulate the non-linear behaviour of orthotropic or anisotropic solids such as fibre-reinforced composites is a complex task. After the first attempts to formulate yield functions for orthotropic materials by extending the isotropic Von Mises yield function (called Hill yield function), several authors proposed other yield functions in the anisotropic stress space (Bassani, Budiansky, Barlat). Many authors have used four rank tensors in the formulation of yield functions for anisotropic materials. In 1995, Voyiadjis and Thiagarajan proposed a general yield surface, which depends on a four rank tensor and applied this model to study the behaviour of unidirectional fibre-reinforced composites.

The anisotropic theory presented here is based on the ideas proposed by Betten [6] and uses the concept of *mapped stress tensor*. This concept makes it possible to use the advantages and algorithms of the well-known isotropic formulations; consequently, it has many computational advantages. The basic idea consists in modelling the behaviour of a solid in the *real anisotropic space* by means of an ideal solid in a *fictitious isotropic space*. According to Betten, the main hypothesis is that the elastic strains are the same in both spaces, which introduces a limitation in the anisotropic mapped theory. This limitation emanates from the necessary proportionality between the strength limit and the elasticity modulus for each material direction (Oller *et al.*)[7].

All the information on the material anisotropy is contained in fourth order *space transformation* tensors relating the stresses and strains in the real (anisotropic) and fictitious (isotropic) spaces. The parameters that define the transformation tensors can be found from adequate experimental tests.

The traditional procedures to obtain the constitutive equations for anisotropic elastoplastic materials are based on the description of a yield and plastic potential surfaces in terms of the characteristic properties of the material. In this case, it is difficult to satisfy the invariance conditions. Alternatively, if the properties of the real anisotropic solid are defined in terms of a fictitious isotropic solid through a linear relationship between both spaces, the invariance conditions are satisfied (Oller *et al.*)[8]:

$$\bar{\mathbf{s}}_{ij} = A_{ijkl}^s \mathbf{s}_{kl}$$

\mathbf{s}_{kl} and $\bar{\mathbf{s}}_{ij}$ are the stress tensor in the real anisotropic and fictitious isotropic spaces

respectively and A_{ijkl}^s is a fourth order tensor called *space transformation tensor*, which relates the stress in the real and fictitious spaces.

$$A_{ijkl}^s = \bar{s}_{ij} (\mathbf{s}_{kl})^{-1}$$

The relationship between elastic strains in both spaces is defined as:

$$\bar{e}_{ij}^e = A_{ijkl}^e e_{kl}^e$$

This assumption implies non-uniqueness of elastic strains when the change of space is produced. The fourth order transformation tensor, A_{ijkl}^e can be expressed as (Car *et al.*)[2]:

$$A_{rsmn}^e = \left[\bar{C}_{irks} \right]^{-1} A_{ijkl}^s C_{jlmn}$$

where \bar{C}_{ikrs} and C_{jlmn} are the constitutive tensors in the fictitious and real spaces, relating stresses and strains in the standard manner. Note that C_{jlmn} includes the actual properties of the material, whereas the choice of \bar{C}_{ikrs} can be arbitrary and for this purpose the property of any known material can be chosen. The figure 3 shows the different space transformations and the changes in the shape of the yield functions.

Fig. 3 Anisotropic Real Space and Isotropic Fictitious Space Transformations

The *yield function* and the *potential function* are defined respectively in the following way:

$$f(\mathbf{s}; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = 0 \quad g(\mathbf{s}; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = K$$

where \mathbf{s} is the stress tensor in the real anisotropic space and α_s^m the set of internal elasto-plastic variables. By means of the four order transformation tensor the yield function and the potential function for the anisotropic material can be written in terms of the stress tensor in the fictitious isotropic stress as:

$$f(\mathbf{s}; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = \bar{f}(\mathbf{s}; A^s; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = \bar{f}(\mathbf{S}; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = 0$$

$$g(\mathbf{s}; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = \bar{g}(\mathbf{s}; A^s; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = \bar{g}(\mathbf{S}; \mathbf{a}_s^m) = K$$

It should be considered that the dissipation is invariant between the anisotropic and isotropic spaces. As a consequence of the *uniqueness of the dissipation* it is irrelevant to write the constitutive model in either spaces (Car *et al.*)[2]:

$$\bar{\Xi}_{mec} = \mathbf{s}_{ij} : \dot{\mathbf{e}}_{ij} - m \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \dot{\mathbf{a}} = \bar{\mathbf{s}}_{ij} : \dot{\bar{\mathbf{e}}}_{ij} - m \frac{\partial \mathbf{y}}{\partial \mathbf{a}} \dot{\mathbf{a}} \geq 0$$

The previous expressions show that it is equivalent to write the constitutive model in the anisotropic real space or in the equivalent isotropic fictitious one. Obviously, writing the constitutive models in the isotropic fictitious space allows to profit from the advantages and algorithms used for isotropic materials.

MICROMECHANIC APPROACH TO THE EFFECTIVE ELASTIC PROPERTIES

The constitutive models based on the *Mixing Theory* assume that in each material point all the component substances contribute at the same time and with their own constitutive law in the assigned volume proportion. This allows combining materials with different constitutive behaviour (elastic, elasto-plastic, elasto-brittle, etc.) as it has been shown in the previous section. For this reason, the constitutive equations of the constituents should be carefully introduced in the model. This section deals with the definition of the elastic properties of the constituents of glass fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites.

To simulate this composite material, a standard plasticity model has been chosen for the matrix, whereas the behaviour of the fibre reinforcement is modelled by means of the anisotropic elasto-plastic model. Let E_m be the Young's modulus of the matrix and E_f that of the fibre. The contribution of the stiffness of the constituents on the stiffness of the composite is not an easy matter to solve. In a very simple case, which is a unidirectional (UD) lamina, it has been possible to deduce analytic expressions for the elastic properties of the composite in the direction parallel and perpendicular to the fibre. This kind of studies that relate the macroscopic properties of the UD lamina with the properties of the constituents and their volume fraction are called micro-mechanic studies. In most of them it is necessary to admit reasonably but strong approximations like perfect interface between constituents or a complete elastic behaviour of the material.

These micro-mechanic approaches range from simple parallel or serial behaviour, which assume that the constituents are under the same level of strain or stress, respectively, to more

sophisticated models that simulate the composite through the periodic repetition of a representative volume. Finite element calculations have also been carried out to estimate this micromechanics question. Moreover, it exists a considerable amount of experimental data that has permitted to validate these models.

The experimental studies show that the elastic modulus of the UD lamina in the direction of the fibre (E_{11}) follows the mixing theory (also named *rule of mixtures*). That is, the constituents exhibit a parallel behaviour:

$$E_{11} = E_f k_f + E_m (1 - k_f)$$

Other elastic properties of the composite, such as the in-plane Poisson modulus ν_{12} do follow the same theory. However, the other independent elastic properties of the UD lamina (E_{22} , G_{12} and G_{23}) are not well represented by assuming this theory. As an example, among the micro-mechanical theories, the simplest one to estimate the stiffness of the UD composite in the transverse direction, E_{22} , assumes a strict serial behaviour:

$$\frac{1}{E_{22}} = \frac{1}{E_f} k_f + \frac{1}{E_m} (1 - k_f)$$

However, the constitutive model presented in the previous section is based on the hypothesis of parallel behaviour of the constituents. The apparent contradiction between this assumption and the behaviour observed experimentally requires the introduction of the modification of the properties of the material so that the formalism of the mixing theory can be conserved. It is necessary to define an equivalent stiffness of the fibre E_f^* and of the matrix E_m^* , obeying:

$$E_{22} = E_f^* = E_m^* \quad E_{22} = E_f^* k_f + E_m^* (1 - k_f)$$

where E_{22} results from a micro-mechanical model, such as: strict parallel behaviour (also called Reuss Approximation), semi-experimental Halpin-Tsai model or others analytical approximations such as Gibson and Chamis.

Fig 4. Different micro-mechanics predictions for the transverse axial modulus for glass/epoxy unidirectional layer for different participation of fibre.

This definition of the stiffness of the equivalent material obeys to the fact that their stress is the same as that of the real material. Therefore, identical yield and potential plastic functions in real and equivalent materials can be used. The actual strains are derived from equivalent material strains according to

$$\mathbf{e}_f = \frac{E_f^*}{E_f} \mathbf{e}_f^* = \frac{E_{22}}{E_f} \mathbf{e}_f^* \quad \mathbf{e}_m = \frac{E_m^*}{E_m} \mathbf{e}_m^* = \frac{E_{22}}{E_m} \mathbf{e}_m^*$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three configurations of E-glass/epoxy laminates have been studied: $[0^\circ]_4$ unidirectional, $[90^\circ]_4$ unidirectional and cross-ply laminate $[0^\circ, 90^\circ]_{3s}$. The coupons were tested under pure tension according to the standard ASTM D3039. The experimental behaviour until fracture has been compared to the numerical results of the constitutive model.

The figure 5 compares the experimental results and the model response for a UD laminate. The 0° laminate exhibits a good correspondence between model and experiment for both the stress-strain dependence and the strength limit. However, in the 90° laminate the results show large divergences. On the one hand the stiffness obtained from the micro-mechanical model (Chamis)[9] is lower than the experimental. On the other hand, the model strength is higher for the experimental results. This is due to the appearance of the debonding phenomenon in the fibre-matrix interface when the fibre is oriented perpendicular to the stress. Therefore, the adherence limit values has been inferred from this divergence. This parameter has been introduced in the model to simulate the behaviour of the cross-ply laminate.

Fig.5. Experimental and modelled results of the UD laminate: $[0^\circ]$ (left) and $[90^\circ]$ (right)

Figure 7 shows the simulation and experimental result of the strain-stress dependence for the cross-ply laminate with 10% of the fibres oriented at 0° and 90% at 90° .

As a conclusion, a constitutive model based on the mixing theory has been shown to reproduce the elastoplastic behaviour of a polymer-matrix glass fibre-reinforced composite material. However, it has been evidenced that some refinements should be introduced to simulate the

experimental behaviour. Further work, will focus on the improvement of the closing equation to account for the non-parallel behaviour. An extensive micromechanical study will be required for this purpose.

Fig.6. Experimental and modelled stress-strain dependence of the cross-ply laminate [0°,90°]

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